

Music Generation using Machine learning

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Abstract— In recent years there has been growing interest in creating music using machine learning. For computer scientists and musicians alike, the application of machine learning to music creation presents exciting opportunities. It makes it possible to compose music that is not only original but also suited to particular genres and styles. This paper introduces a methodology to music generation using LSTM neural networks, a type of recurrent Neural Networks designed for sequential data.

Keywords—LSTM, Midi, Recurrent Neural network

I. INTRODUCTON

With the introduction of deep learning and artificial intelligence, the field of music generation has undergone profound improvements. We are able to generate pitch and duration sequences for the composition of entire songs by building a robust network of LSTMs [2]. This paper presents the application of an LSTM network for music generation, along with a brief, intelligible overview of the theory and intuition behind LSTMs and their use in music sequence modelling. We also show the qualitative influence on our model output, investigate potential network improvements, and weigh the benefits and drawbacks of our network and training data.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Currently, several methods are used to produce a musical composition, and their combination might be applied to create a novel and effective model [3]. We categorise these methods into two broad groups. Two methods of creating music are conventional algorithms that follow predetermined functions and an autonomous model that learns from the previous structure of musical notes to create new music.

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks have emerged as a transformative force in the realm of music generation [1]. These neural networks, which fall under the broader category of recurrent neural networks (RNNs), have proven to be exceptionally well-suited for capturing intricate musical patterns and generating harmonious compositions [4]. This can be seen in a 2017 article [6] by Sigurður Skúli, a Machine learning Engineer, titled 'Music generation using Keras'.

Another tool is MuseGAN, a generative adversarial network (GAN) designed for the generation of symbolic multi-track music. MuseGAN represents a noteworthy

development in the field of AI-generated music, offering the capability to create complex musical compositions across multiple tracks or instruments

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Gathering and Preparing Data:

Data Collection: In this study, we collected a vast corpus of musical compositions spanning various artists and composers. The data collection is in midi format, which is often used by musical composers and the output of musical instruments. This is collected from the Kaggle Dataset.

From the midi files we can access note objects using music21 library in python. Pitch, octave, offset, and other crucial information about a particular musical note are all contained within note objects. Pitch, which is represented by the letters A through G, with A standing for the highest pitch and G for the lowest, indicates the frequency or tonal quality of the sound. Octave, which is similar to the divisions on a piano keyboard, indicates the range of pitches that the note falls inside. On the other hand, offset describes the note's temporal positioning inside the musical piece.

Data Preprocessing: Since the most important components of the note can be replicated using the pitch's string notation, we append the pitch of each note object using its string notation. Also, we add each chord by converting the note of all the chord's notes into a single string, with a dot between each note.

```
from music21 import converter, instrument, note, chord
notes = []
for file in glob.glob("mozart/*.mid"):
    midi = converter.parse(file)

    print("Parsing %s" % file)

    notes_to_parse = None

    try:
        s2 = instrument.partitionByInstrument(midi)
        notes_to_parse = s2.parts[0].recurse()
    except:
        notes_to_parse = midi.flat.notes

    for element in notes_to_parse:
        if isinstance(element, note.Note):
            notes.append(str(element.pitch))
        elif isinstance(element, chord.Chord):
            notes.append('.'.join(str(n) for n in element.normalOrder))

print(notes)
```

The script iterates through a list of midi files into the directory. On each midi file it parses the midi using the converter function. The instrument parts are then saved to a variable. The last loop iterates and checks whether the object is a note or a chord. The chords are broken down to individual notes.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

Our model consists of four primary types of layers: LSTM layers, Dropout layers, Dense layers, and Activation layers. Each of these components plays a crucial role in the network's ability to learn and generate music sequences.

```
model = Sequential()
model.add(LSTM(
    256,
    input_shape=(network_input.shape[1], network_input.shape[2]),
    return_sequences=True
))
model.add(Dropout(0.3))
model.add(LSTM(512, return_sequences=True))
model.add(Dropout(0.3))
model.add(LSTM(256))
model.add(Dense(256))
model.add(Dropout(0.3))
model.add(Dense(n_vocab))
model.add(Activation('softmax'))
model.compile(loss='categorical_crossentropy', optimizer='rmsprop')
```

Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are built on LSTM layers, which are especially useful for processing sequential data. RNN often have issues with gradient explosion, so LSTM model are preferred in our approach [5]. In the described model, there are three LSTM layers. Each LSTM layer contains multiple nodes, or memory cells, which can capture and store information over sequential time steps. The return_sequences=True setting in the first two LSTM layers indicates that they should return sequences of output, allowing them to maintain temporal information. The final LSTM layer doesn't have this setting and outputs a fixed-size vector.

Dropout Layers: In order to keep neural networks from overfitting, dropout layers are used. When a network becomes overly specialized in learning the training set and struggles to generalize to new data, this is known as overfitting. During training, the dropout layers deactivate a portion of the provided input units at random. This architecture applies a thirty percent percentage of dropouts following each LSTM layer.

Dense Layers: Dense Layers: In a dense neural network, every input node is connected to every output node and vice versa. In this architecture, there are two dense layers. The first dense layer with 256 nodes connects the output of the third LSTM layer to the following layers. Dense layers allow the network to combine and process the information learned by the LSTM layers, providing a transition from the LSTM-generated features to the final output layer.

Activation Layer: The activation layer determines what activation function is used to calculate the output of a node. In this architecture, 'softmax' activation is applied. 'Softmax' activation is commonly used in multi-class classification problems like music generation. It transforms the network's output into a probability distribution over all possible classes.

The network is trained using Keras' model.fit() function. A checkpoint is created so that on each epoch the model is saved. This allows to resume the training of the model without losing an y weight. The list of input sequences that we previously prepared is the first parameter; the list of corresponding outputs is the second. In our training we will be using 200 epochs.

V. RESULTS

The results are saved to local machine. The midi obtained when data trained on a midi dataset of the popular composer Beethoven can be played using a midi compatible player. When the mid file is converted to sheet music, the results is as follows.

Similarly, the results of a model trained on game music is as follows:

The midi files generated can be played on most devices by converting to a widely supported format such as mp3 or wav.

The files for the above midi generations can be played by visiting the following links.

- [Music generated by Beethoven's model](#)
- [Music generated by game music Model](#)

VI. CONCLUSION

The LSTM model is able to generate melodic music from data of various composers and types of music. One major drawback is that the music sounds too robotic. Midi files does not handle things such as suspense and dynamics of music. Future works may use raw music data and convert them into a suitable format. This can reduce the robotic nature of music and give a bit of soul to the music

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